

Comparison of Arthroscopic Suturing Vs. Open Posterior Approach for Acute Displaced PCL Avulsion

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Abstract:

Background: Injuries involving tibial-side avulsions of the posterior cruciate ligament (PCL) are generally regarded as uncommon. This study aimed to retrospectively evaluate and compare the clinical outcomes of displaced PCL avulsion fractures on the tibial side, managed using either open reduction with screw fixation or arthroscopic suture fixation.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective review was conducted for patients treated surgically for displaced PCL tibial-side avulsion. The study included cases showing radiographic displacement exceeding 3 mm and/or grade II or III posterior laxity as determined by the posterior drawer test. Associated injuries were addressed appropriately, and a conservative rehabilitation protocol was implemented until radiologic confirmation of fracture healing. Data from clinicoradiologic evaluations at the 1-year follow-up were analyzed to compare outcomes between the two groups.

Results: 78 patients with 1-year follow-up data were included, comprising 39 in the open reduction group and 39 in the arthroscopic fixation group. Over 90% of patients in both groups reported normal or nearly normal knee function. At 1 year, knee function outcomes, as assessed by the Lysholm score and Tegner activity level, were comparable between the groups. Performance on the one-leg hop test was also similar. However, postoperative arthrometric laxity measurements with indicated better stability in the arthroscopic group compared to that in the open group. Fracture union was typically achieved within three months post-surgery, and no significant complications were observed.

Conclusion: Both open reduction with screw fixation and arthroscopic suture fixation resulted in comparable short-term clinical outcomes, radiologic fracture healing, and knee stability for patients with PCL tibial-side avulsion fractures. However, arthroscopic fixation demonstrated slightly superior postoperative laxity outcomes.

Keywords: Posterior cruciate ligament, Open reduction, Arthroscopy, Fracture.

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Introduction

Tibial-side avulsion fractures of the posterior cruciate ligament (PCL) are typically regarded as uncommon injuries. However, in regions with a high incidence of motorcycle accidents, these bony avulsion injuries of the PCL are relatively more frequent. It is widely accepted that displaced tibial-side avulsions of the PCL should be anatomically reduced and stabilized. Early fixation, ideally within the first 3 weeks, is recommended for displaced PCL avulsion fractures [1-3]. Both open [4-6] and arthroscopic [7-10] fixation techniques have been associated with favorable outcomes,

although only few case series have documented the use of arthroscopic methods to date [11-14]. One biomechanical study has indicated that screw fixation via open techniques yields comparable results to suture fixation performed arthroscopically [15]. Nevertheless, there remains a gap in comparative clinical studies assessing open versus arthroscopic techniques. This study aimed to retrospectively evaluate the clinical outcomes of displaced tibial-side PCL avulsion fractures treated with either open reduction and screw fixation or arthroscopic suture fixation. The hypothesis was

that both groups would show comparable clinical and radiological outcomes, with no statistically significant difference in laxity measurements during short-term follow-up.

Material and Methods

A retrospective review was conducted on all surgically treated displaced tibial-side avulsion fractures of the PCL at our tertiary care hospital and trauma center. Initially, all cases were managed via an open posterior approach, whereas arthroscopic techniques were implemented subsequently.

The inclusion criteria for this study encompassed: tibial-side PCL avulsion fractures presenting with radiographic evidence of upward displacement exceeding 3 mm, or those exhibiting grade II (5–10 mm of translation) or grade III (>10 mm of translation) on the posterior drawer test at 90° of knee flexion during clinical or anesthesia examination. Associated injuries to the meniscus, cartilage, anterior cruciate ligament (ACL), or collateral ligaments did not disqualify the cases. Exclusion criteria included fractures of the proximal tibia or distal femur, open fractures, or concurrent neurovascular damage.

Radiographic confirmation of all avulsion fractures was performed using X-rays, CT scan, or MRI. CT scans were utilized to evaluate the size, comminution, and displacement of the fracture fragments, while MRI was employed when collateral ligament or posterolateral corner injuries were suspected. Preoperative clinical assessment included testing with the Lachman, anterior and posterior drawer tests to assess cruciate ligament damage, as well as varus and valgus stress tests in both extension and 30° flexion to evaluate the integrity of the collateral ligaments. Additional tests, such as the dial and external rotation recurvatum tests, were conducted to examine potential posterolateral corner injuries.

In the operating room, the injured knee was thoroughly evaluated under anesthesia, and any observed laxity was recorded. Both the open and arthroscopic techniques employed were adapted from established methods in the literature and were confirmed to be safe through cadaveric dissection verification [16].

The rehabilitation protocol was consistent across both groups, including those with associated collateral ligament injuries. In the immediate postoperative period, a knee immobilizer brace was used to maintain full extension, and a 2-inch thick cotton pad was placed behind the calf to protect the PCL.

Patients were encouraged to begin partial weight-bearing with the assistance of axillary crutches,

along with quadriceps strengthening and isometric exercises. Starting from the third week, assisted range of motion exercises were introduced in the prone position using a hinged knee brace, initially allowing 0° to 30° flexion, gradually increasing to 120° by six weeks. Stationary bicycling was permitted thereafter. The use of the knee brace was discontinued when radiologic healing was achieved, and full activity was resumed.

Patients were followed up and evaluated with both clinical and radiographic assessments at monthly intervals until fracture union occurred, followed by a final evaluation at 1 year postoperatively. At the 1-year follow-up, in addition to clinical evaluation, knee stability was assessed using an arthrometer noting any side-to-side differences. The Lysholm score, Tegner activity scale, International Knee Documentation Committee (IKDC) knee ligament examination form, and single-leg hop test were used to document symptoms and functional outcomes. Knee radiographs in standing anteroposterior and lateral views were analyzed for alignment, joint space narrowing, and degenerative changes. The severity of degenerative changes was classified according to the Ahlbäck grading system. The outcomes at 1 year were used for comparative evaluation between the two groups.

The data collected were analyzed using SPSS software (version 23.0). The results were compared between the two groups using the unpaired Student's t-test for continuous variables, Fisher's exact test for nominal data, and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test for ordered categorical variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The patient profile under study, as shown in Table 1, includes key characteristics of the Open Group (n=39) and Arthroscopy Group (n=39). The two groups were similar in terms of gender distribution, with a slightly higher number of males in both groups. The difference in age between the two groups was not statistically significant (P=0.32). However, there was a notable difference in the time to surgery, with the Open Group undergoing surgery earlier (6.4 ± 4.4 days) compared to the Arthroscopy Group (8.2 ± 2.4 days).

Regarding associated injuries, the groups differed significantly in terms of ACL injuries, with 12 cases observed in the Arthroscopy Group and none in the Open Group (P=0.10). Other associated injuries, including medial meniscus, MCL, LCL, and lateral meniscus, did not show any significant differences between the two groups. In terms of posterior instability in anesthesia, the distribution of grades was similar between the two groups, with no significant differences (P=0.78).

Table 1: Patient profile under study

Characteristic	Open Group (n=39)	Arthroscopy Group (n=39)	P Value
Total Cases, n	39	39	-
Age, Mean \pm SD	28.6 \pm 8.2	26.8 \pm 7.5	0.32
Time to surgery, Mean \pm SD	6.4 \pm 4.4	8.2 \pm 2.4	0.03
Male, n	36	35	0.69
Female, n	3	4	
Associated Injuries, n			
ACL	0	12	0.10
Medial Meniscus	0	4	
MCL	3	2	
LCL	3	2	
Lateral Meniscus	0	2	
Posterior Instability in Anesthesia, n			
Grade 1	0	0	0.78
Grade 2	26	23	
Grade 3	13	16	

Table 2 compares the laxity between the two groups at 1 year postoperatively using various tests. For the Anterior Drawer Test, no significant differences were observed, with the majority of both groups showing Grade 1 laxity.

Similarly, for the Lachman Test, the Open Group had 5 cases of Grade 1, while the Arthroscopy Group had 3, but the difference was not significant

($P=0.48$). The Posterior Drawer Test revealed a higher number of Grade 1 laxity in the Open Group (20 vs. 17), but this difference was also not statistically significant ($P=0.62$).

In the Valgus in Extension Test, the Open Group had 2 cases of Grade 1 laxity, compared to 1 in the Arthroscopy Group ($P=0.56$), again showing no significant difference.

Table 2: Comparison of Laxity at 1 year postoperatively

Test	Grade	Open Group (n=39)	Arthroscopy Group (n=39)	p Value
Anterior Drawer Test	Grade 1	4	3	0.71
	Grade 2	0	0	-
	Grade 3	0	0	-
Lachman Test	Grade 1	5	3	0.48
	Grade 2	1	0	0.68
	Grade 3	0	0	-
Posterior Drawer Test	Grade 1	20	17	0.62
	Grade 2	7	3	0.21
	Grade 3	0	0	-
Valgus in Extension	Grade 1	2	1	0.56
	Grade 2	0	0	-
	Grade 3	0	0	-

Table 3 compares postoperative outcomes between the two groups. Postoperatively, both groups had high and nearly identical Lysholm Scores (94.1 \pm 6.2 for the Open Group and 94.1 \pm 7.4 for the Arthroscopy Group), suggesting no difference in functional recovery between the groups.

In terms of the Tegner Activity Level, both groups reported a significant improvement postoperatively. Regarding the range of motion, the Open Group showed a mean of 117.3 \pm 10.3 $^\circ$ and the Arthroscopy Group had 120.1 \pm 12.0 $^\circ$, with no

significant difference ($P=0.45$). The laxity on arthrometer measurement (side-to-side difference) did not show significant differences between the groups. For the final IKDC rating, both groups had a similar distribution, with the majority rated as "Normal" (20 in each group), and no significant difference was observed ($P=0.98$).

Lastly, the One-Leg Hop Test showed no significant difference in the proportion of patients achieving >90% performance, indicating similar functional outcomes between the groups.

Table 3: Comparison of outcomes post-operatively

Test	Open Group (n=39)	Arthroscopy Group (n=39)	p Value
Lysholm Score			
Preoperative	34.0 ± 8.8	35.6 ± 8.2	0.85
Postoperative	94.1 ± 6.2	94.1 ± 7.4	
Tegner Activity Level			
Preinjury	6.8 ± 1.7	6.8 ± 1.5	0.69
Preoperative	3.0 ± 1.5	3.1 ± 1.3	
Postoperative	6.5 ± 1.6	6.7 ± 1.4	
Range of Motion (°)	117.3 ± 10.3	120.1 ± 12.0	0.45
Laxity on Arthrometer (Side-to-Side Difference)			
0-3 mm	29	33	0.42
3-5 mm	10	6	
>5 mm	0	0	
Final IKDC Rating			
Normal	20	20	0.98
Nearly Normal	16	15	
Abnormal	3	4	
Severely Abnormal	0	0	
One-Leg Hop Test			
>90%	30	31	0.76
76%-90%	6	4	
50%-75%	3	4	

Discussion

Both arthroscopic and open treatment methods for tibial-side PCL avulsion injuries resulted in favorable clinical outcomes, satisfactory radiographic healing, and low complication rates. All patients exhibited strong functional performance when comparing the injured limb to the uninjured contralateral extremity.

Previous case series on open fixation techniques have consistently reported good or fair outcomes in more than 90% of patients [5,6,17,18]. Similarly, the four case series on arthroscopic fixation found excellent healing within three months, with 90% to 100% of patients rating their knee as normal or nearly normal [19-22]. Our findings demonstrate similar results in both groups, aligning with the existing literature.

Inoue et al. [23] observed that nearly 50% of patients with PCL avulsion fractures showed high signal intensity on T2-weighted MRI scans, suggesting the presence of occult midsubstance ligament injuries. However, this did not appear to influence postoperative posterior laxity in a comparative study. Gui et al. [13] noted that 50% of patients with PCL avulsions exhibited plastic deformation of the ligament upon arthroscopic evaluation.

Despite these significant interstitial injuries, most studies reported excellent clinical outcomes; side-to-side laxity of less than 3 mm was noted in 86% [11], 94.4% [14], 96% [13], and 97% [12] of cases. We hypothesize that interstitial injury to the PCL

may heal without causing laxity, especially when the ligament is held taut by fixation. In our cohort, side-to-side laxity of less than 3 mm was observed in 74% of patients in the open group and 85% in the arthroscopic group. Earlier reports have recommended cast immobilization for six weeks following fixation of displaced PCL avulsion fractures [4,14,19,20], but this approach has been linked to a high incidence of joint stiffness [1]. Functional bracing and early mobilization protocols have been implemented in a limited number of studies [21].

In our study, we employed an early mobilization protocol with a hinged brace, as the fixation was deemed stable. No hardware failure or radiographic displacement of screws occurred.

The strengths of this study include the large sample size, the comparative nature of the analysis between open and arthroscopic techniques, and the involvement of multiple surgeons, which underscores the reproducibility of both methods.

Conclusion

Both the arthroscopic and open posterior techniques for treating PCL tibial-side avulsion fractures demonstrated comparable positive clinical outcomes, radiological healing, and knee stability during short-term follow-up assessments.

References

1. Bali K, Prabhakar S, Saini U, Dhillon MS. Open reduction and internal fixation of isolated PCL fossa avulsion fractures. *Knee Surg*

- Sports Traumatol Arthrosc. 2012; 20(2):315-321.
2. Shino K, Nakata K, Mae T, Yamada Y, Shiozaki Y, Toritsuka Y. Arthroscopic fixation of tibial bony avulsion of the posterior cruciate ligament. *Arthroscopy*. 2003; 19(9):E12.
 3. Trickey EL. Injuries to the posterior cruciate ligament: Diagnosis and treatment of early injuries and reconstruction of late instability. *Clin Orthop Relat Res*. 1980; (147):76-81.
 4. Jazayeri SM, Esmaili Jah AA, Karami M. A safe posteromedial approach to posterior cruciate ligament avulsion fracture. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc*. 2009; 17(3):244-247.
 5. Nicandri GT, Klineberg EO, Wahl CJ, Mills WJ. Treatment of posterior cruciate ligament tibial avulsion fractures through a modified open posterior approach: Operative technique and 12- to 48-month outcomes. *J Orthop Trauma*. 2008; 22(5):317-324.
 6. Zhang CL, Xu H, Li MQ. Posteromedial approach of gastrocnemius for reduction and internal fixation of avulsed tibial attachment of posterior cruciate ligament. *Chin J Traumatol*. 2006; 9(1):25-28.
 7. Kwon OS, Park MJ, Kelly JD IV. Arthroscopic treatment of a PCL avulsion fracture in a skeletally immature patient. *Orthopedics*. 2011; 34(3):137.
 8. Wajsfisz A, Makridis KG, Van Den Steene JY, Djian P. Fixation of posterior cruciate ligament avulsion fracture with the use of a suspensory fixation. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc*. 2012; 20(6):996-999.
 9. Gwinner C, Kopf S, Hoburg A, Haas NP, Jung TM. Arthroscopic treatment of acute tibial avulsion fracture of the posterior cruciate ligament using the tightrope fixation device. *Arthrosc Tech*. 2014; 3(5):e377-e382.
 10. Horas U, Meissner SA, Heiss C, Schnettler R. Arthroscopic fixation of posterior cruciate ligament avulsion fractures: A new minimally invasive technique. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc*. 2010; 18(6):781-783.
 11. Kim SJ, Shin SJ, Choi NH, Cho SK. Arthroscopically assisted treatment of avulsion fractures of the posterior cruciate ligament from the tibia. *J Bone Joint Surg Am*. 2001; 83(5):698-708.
 12. Zhao J, He Y, Wang J. Arthroscopic treatment of acute tibial avulsion fracture of the posterior cruciate ligament with suture fixation technique through Y-shaped bone tunnels. *Arthroscopy*. 2006; 22(2):172-181.
 13. Gui J, Wang L, Jiang Y, Wang Q, Yu Z, Gu Q. Single tunnel suture fixation of posterior cruciate ligament avulsion fracture. *Arthroscopy*. 2009; 25(1):78-85.
 14. Chen SY, Cheng CY, Chang SS, et al. Arthroscopic suture fixation for avulsion fracture in the tibial attachment of the posterior cruciate ligament. *Arthroscopy*. 2012; 28(10):1454-1463.
 15. Sasaki SU, da Mota e Albuquerque RF, Amatzuzi MM, Pereira CA. Open screw fixation versus arthroscopic suture fixation of tibial posterior cruciate ligament avulsion injuries: A mechanical comparison. *Arthroscopy*. 2007; 23(12):1226-1230.
 16. Sabat D, Jain A, Kumar V. Displaced Posterior Cruciate Ligament Avulsion Fractures: A Retrospective Comparative Study between Open Posterior Approach and Arthroscopic Single-Tunnel Suture Fixation. *Arthroscopy*. 2016 Jan; 32(1):44-53.
 17. Dhillon MS, Singh HP, Nagi ON. Posterior cruciate ligament avulsion from the tibia: Fixation by a posteromedial approach. *Acta Orthop Belg*. 2003; 69(2):162-167.
 18. Jazayeri SM, Esmaili Jah AA, Karami M. A safe posteromedial approach to posterior cruciate ligament avulsion fracture. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc*. 2009; 17(3):244-247.
 19. Littlejohn SG, Geissler WB. Arthroscopic repair of a posterior cruciate ligament avulsion. *Arthroscopy*. 1995; 11(3):235-238.
 20. Choi NH, Kim SJ. Arthroscopic reduction and fixation of bony avulsion of the posterior cruciate ligament of the tibia. *Arthroscopy*. 1997; 13(6):759-762.
 21. Arevalo R, Urbano V, Montanez E, Martin F. Arthroscopic repair of the posterior cruciate ligament: Two techniques. *Arthroscopy*. 2000; 16(6):656-660.
 22. Deehan DJ, Pinczewski LA. Arthroscopic reattachment of an avulsion fracture of the tibial insertion of the posterior cruciate ligament. *Arthroscopy*. 2001; 17(4):422-425.
 23. Inoue M, Yasuda K, Kondo E, Saito K, Ishibe M. Primary repair of posterior cruciate ligament avulsion fracture. The effect of occult injury in the midsubstance on postoperative instability. *Am J Sports Med* 2004; 32:1230-1237.